

**WHATSAPP VOICE CHAT (WVC) AS AN EFL ONLINE
LEARNING MEDIA AT ENGLISH CLUB OF SMPIT INSAN
KAMIL SIDOARJO**

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to figure out the steps of implementation one of the features of the Whatsapp Messenger application, namely Voice chat as an online learning media for students at English club of SMPIT Insan Kamil Sidoarjo. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative method. The population in this study were all English Club members of SMPIT Insan Kamil Sidoarjo. The sample of this research is a chairman and 20 members of the English Club, as well as eight members to find out the student's response. In this study, there were three stages, the first was pre-activity. at this stage, the teacher provides material reinforcement during class learning. The second is the Whilst activity, at this stage the teacher gives instructions using Whatsapp text combined with Whatsapp voice notes. At this stage students also implement the instructions given by the teacher using Whatsapp voice notes. After that, students fill out the submission list sent by the teacher. The third stage is the closing activity, in this activity the teacher provides feedback in the form of evaluating and appreciating the results of student performance. In student responses, it was found that six out of eight students interviewed stated that they felt happy with the online learning through Whatsapp voice chat. Suggestions for other researchers to investigate the effectiveness of using

features such as video calling to improve students' English skills.

Key Words: Whatsapp, Online learning, Media

INTRODUCTION

In the era of the development of science and technology, language is one thing that cannot be separated from the role of human life. With language we can express emotions, ideas, and desires. Language is also used as a medium or tool to communicate with others. One of the most important languages to learn is English. The reason why it is important to learn English is because English is an international language. Given the importance of English proficiency, many countries, including Indonesia, make English the primary subject taught in schools.

In recent years, researcher interested in mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) for online learning of English as a foreign language (EFL). In the current era of digitalization, access to information and materials can be easily found in cyberspace, either by accessing a page or by using an application. With these advances in technology, can be used as a tool to facilitate the educational process. The Ministry of Education and Culture is aware of the current needs, because by utilizing technology it can reach and distribute broad policies, as well as optimize the implementation of the Merdeka curriculum. As a teacher, this is a challenge in itself to bring students to learning transformation, where the teacher acts as a facilitator to encourage the learning process (Insiyah, 2018).

Technology that applied in online learning to help students increase in out-of-class language learning experiences (Lai and Gu,

2011). Learning outside the classroom using mobile phones is "the richest vein of language learning potential, in that students may engage in a variety of informal learning activities: incidental (e.g., gameplay), instrumental (e.g., use of a language learning service or app), or accidental (e.g., code-switching in a YouTube video)" (Godwin-Jones, 2017). Using this type of audiovisual technology, sources of original language input for either formal or informal learning can be easily found by learners of both English as a second language (ESL) and a foreign language (EFL).

In today's technological developments and new curriculum, it demands teachers to be more creative in choosing the right media in the teaching and learning process. In the media taxonomy, Rudi Breetz divides eight media classifications, namely dynamic audiovisual media, silent audiovisual media, semi-dynamic sound, animation, still images, semi-animation, sound and printing (Sadiman, 2021). In giving learning activity to students, they must also use appropriate and varied media, by avoiding boredom for students. One of the media that can be used is social media. Social media is a potentially power tool in education (Almodiel, 2017). Social media is an example of technological developments that are useful in the world of education if used with the right methods. One of the social media that the researchers focused on in this research was called Whatsapp.

In the context of learning a foreign language, the acquisition of speaking skills is imperative, especially in the case of learning English. Effectively communicating in English is a crucial aspect of language acquisition, and the teacher experienced the repercussions of this during in-person meetings. According to Brown (2000), the demonstration of an ability to achieve practical goals through interactive dialogue with other

speakers is a key indicator of successfully acquiring a language. Therefore, speaking plays a vital role in learning English as a foreign language, enabling learners to effectively communicate in the target language and achieve their language learning goals.

Widad (2021) with his research which discussed testing the challenges of teaching in a virtual classroom using Whatsapp during a pandemic. The researcher used a qualitative descriptive method with the subject of three English teachers and eight MA Darul Falah students, Cermee Bondowoso. In the study it was concluded that there were several challenges faced by students and teachers in virtual classrooms using Whatsapp during the pandemic such as unstable internet networks, different telephone capacities, and lack of interaction between teachers and students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Nature of MALL

Mobile phones with advanced capabilities have expanded into all aspects of human existence, including language learning. Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) is the application of mobile technologies to language acquisition (Tayabeh and Amin, 2012). The use mobile phone in learning language makes the learning becomes intuitive, informal, individual, and flexible. Convenience features and specifications such as being easy to carry everywhere, the pad design (keypad or touchpad) and audio feature makes mobile phone becomes potential media in learning language environment. Tayabeh and Amin (2012) also added in learning language environment, mobile phone

provides extensive learning, such as giving more chance to learning, variatif learning, and private learning, Although not all learning content and activities are mobile phone accessible. Mobile phone can fasilitate some activities of language learning such as game-based learning, chat-based learning, find word and pronunciation challenge, etc. Those activities are able to facilitate language learning for speaking, vocabulary, listening, grammar, and reading. Beside that, there is also has disadvantage in using mobile phones in language learning. For example, less spesification, limited capacity of storage, and processor speed.

The Use of Voice Chat in MALL

Mobile phones supports various activity related to language learning which can name SMS, camera, audio/video recording, internet access, camera and audio/video messaging. There are many activities can be fasilitated by MALL. One of the activities is voice messaging/chat. Voice chat is available inside the social media application which can use for learning language. Related to this research which uses voice chat as media English online learning for EFL student.

In addition, there is a reason why the use of voice chat in online learning English recomended. First, because it easy to use. Second, it can be interactive activity between the students and teacher. Moreover, voice chat can be a media without the limitation of learning place and time.

The Utilization of Whatsaap

Technically, WhatsApp provided for quick access to the information. The program's straightforward operation concepts make it

accessible to a wide range of users from various ages and backgrounds. Bhounik and Deshen (2014) stated “Anyone having a smartphone, an active internet connection, and the WhatsApp software installed can communicate with anyone”.

Voice Message is one of the many services that WhatsApp offers to make it simple for users to interact with one another. This function allows users to rapidly speak with contacts and groups. It offers a richer chat experience and can be used to transmit crucial and urgent information. Automatic download of this voice message feature occurs.

WhatsApp may be utilized as an English learning tool with this simple process. The teacher can creatively use this program by talking about various motions, providing discussion-worthy photographs, and even using Voice Messages to hear each other's voices. The teachers' role in using WhatsApp as a language learning tool is that of an examiner who assists in correcting and commenting on the students' responses and takes an active position in the conversation (Mistar, 2016).

EFL Online Activity Setting

EFL online activity setting means that the activity provides individualized allows teachers to teach students with varying backgrounds, such as language ability and learning achievements (Soliman, 2016). While the teacher can reach each students in class and provide rapid feedback, the online setting allows students to learn a

foreign language at their own pace, regardless of time or location. Students gain autonomy through online learning by learning on their own (Eneau & Develotte, 2012). As a result, online learning can help EFL students establish learner autonomy, improve their learning attitudes and involvement levels, and boost their confidence and commitment (Kim & Yoon, 2021).

All learning subjects can be taught online such as English. According to Perveen (2016), online learning is an effective medium for English language learning since it allows for the use of a variety of teaching methods, learning styles, and methods. In particular, online learning has been popular as an alternate strategy to teaching and learning in higher education institutions (Famularsih, 2020). The most important aspects of online learning is to know how the implementation online learning itself on their learning experience. Therefore, this research figures out online learning focusing on the use of online media.

The Use of Whatsapp Voice Chat (WVC) in EFL Online Learning

Whatsapp voice chat (WVC) is one of the features of the Whatsapp Messenger Application which is very often used by users because it is easy to use. According to Hanum & Subrata (2021), the WVC feature makes it easy for users to communicate instantly with contacts and groups via voice recordings. In addition, this feature provides a real chat experience and people can use it to convey important factual information. In this research, WVC can be used as an idea to practice EFL students' speaking.

How to use it is the same as the default voice recording application from a mobile phone, but this feature has become a part of the Whatsapp Messenger application, so no need the default voice recording application anymore. So that, This research used procedure adapted from Alireza, Hassan and Karim (2014) research with some

modification in implementing Audio-Recorded in speaking for EFL. First, the teacher explained the instructions, so the students understood what they should do. Second, the teacher gave the example of the task. The example can be the way teacher pronounced the sentences so the students have motivation in learning English.

After that, the students will record the audio of some sentences with certain materials. The materials related to teaching and learning in the class and also students' experience so the ide can be authentic. After the students sent their voice, the teacher give feedback on the studentsperformance. So that, the students' know their weakness in English especially speaking skill.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The Implementation of Whatsapp Voice Chat as an EFL Online Learning Media

Based on the finding data about the implementation of WVC as an EFL online learning media, we can take some discussion. The first was about the teacher giving proper instructions. Data obtained from documentation shows that the teacher implemented students' activity instructions in structured steps. In the three sessions of students' activity instructions, the teacher gave instructions using messages in the form of text and voice notes so that instructions could be conveyed properly and easily understood by students. The success of the instructions delivered cannot be separated from good communication between the teacher and students. Nana Sudjana in Telaumbanua (2018) states that clear communication between teacher and students is effective in achieving

learning objectives. In addition, Based on the clear instruction, more than 75% of students can give positive responses or follow to the instructions.

The second was about the teacher also implementing directly how to pronounce the ten sentences that had been provided by the teacher correctly by using WhatsApp voice chat. This is done so that students can imitate how the teacher pronounces the ten sentences. In similar, using the speaking learning method, namely "Read Aloud", but implemented using Whatsapp voice chat. In Reading Aloud, students practice their speaking by practicing their pronunciation and fluency.

According to Huang (2010) stated one of the functions of Read Aloud is to improve oral English. He added that Reading aloud can be implemented to practice pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary directly so, at the same time they can develop their speaking. Hence, the components of speaking have a correlation with abilities that can be developed through reading aloud. Its supported by the statement from Johnston (2015) who stated that reading aloud can increase their vocabulary development, enhances their speaking ability, especially their fluency and oral language, introduces students to diverse population or cultural diversity and develops critical thinking and problem solving skills. Reading aloud is also useful to improve pronunciation, helps to speak more naturally and confidently, and helps comprehend the text better after reading a text silently.

The third was about the teacher assessed the students with HOTS (High Order Thinking Skills) questions. The teacher gave HOTS questions at the first and third sessions. The first session consist of six questions, and in the third session consist of five questions. The questions are given by the teacher to stimulate the students to be more critical and creative in delivering opinions. This is in accordance with the notion of

HOTS itself. According to Brookhart (2010) and Widana (2017), High Order Thinking Skills consist of the ability to solve problems (problem solving), critical thinking skills (critical thinking), creative thinking (thinking creative), the ability to argue (reasoning), and ability to make decisions (decision making). In addition, Ficayuma (2019) suggested that the productive skills of EFL, such as speaking and writing, should be asses with HOTS skills due to the complexity of macro and micro skills of language. Furthermore, one of the genre texts suggested to assess HOTS is exposition text in factual genre categories and narrative text in story genre categories. In this research, the questions in every session were assigned HOTS, especially in problem-solving and critical thinking, such as the topic of Risk Taker.

From the data of documentation, we can also see that teachers always give appreciation for every work done by students. The teacher gives appreciation in the form of words of compliment delivered via text messages or voice messages on the Whatsapp group. Appreciation received by students can provide intuition and enthusiasm for learning for them to continue to explore their potential (Jamilah et al., 2020). According to Djamarah (2016) appreciation is grouped into several forms and behaviors of educators in giving it such as; the form of gestures, for example, the teacher nods his head, gives applause to the actions of students; Verbal, such as giving praise to students; material, for example providing fun and useful objects for students; in the form of activities, providing opportunities for students to take part in tours or competitions. From observation, the teacher gave appreciation in the form of compilment by example Great job, Girl!.

To make students' abilities increase and learning objectives achieved, the teacher does not forget to complete it by providing an evaluation after learning as a form of improvement of the work that has been done by students. According to Slameto (2015) in his book entitled Educational Evaluation, this evaluation can have two functions, namely formative and summative functions. The formative function is an evaluation that is used to improve and develop ongoing activities. While the summative function is used for accountability, selection, or continuation. In evaluating students, the teacher immediately gives it in the form of a voice message so that it is immediately conveyed and easily understood by students.

On the other hand, From the data research findings, we could see the participants in every session was unstable. The first session, the participants was fifteen students. The second session, the participants was sixteen students. The third session, the participants was nine students. In other words, from the discussion, the EFL online learning using WVC media can be implemented properly, but there is some of students inconsistently following each session.

Students' Respons toward The Implementation of Whatsapp Voice Chat as an EFL Online Learning Media

According to the finding from the data interview, we could take some discussions. First, based on the data of the interview, In the class, the teacher used English, then the teacher translated it into Bahasa to teach and communicate with students which is called Code switching. Code-switching is the alternating use of more than one linguistic code in the classroom by any of the classroom participants such as teacher and students (Lin, 2007). Code-switching used in the class because there are some members of English club from grade seventh

which is a newbie. Code-switching also can motivate students accurately convey meaning and were able to understand by the listener (Junaidi, 2019).

From the finding of the data interview, we could also discuss students' responses and feeling when online learning using WVC. According to students' answer, eight from 8 students, which means 100% of students stated that online learning using voice chat can improve students' speaking skills also grammar, and pronunciation. The data from interview also showed that the reasons why it can improve students' speaking skills was caused the activity encourage students to speak more and more. Another reason was caused the teacher asked the students to pronounce it carefully so that the students could practice their pronunciation. To support the finding of the data, we could see from the last score of English subject the members of English Club in Appendix 3, 95% of students got a final score up to the average of the school minimum standard completeness, which is 75.

In other hand, from the finding interview data we could see two of students state that she did not want online learning anymore. She stated that the sessions made confused and lazy to finished the tasks. In conclusion, dealing with the implementation of Whatsapp voice note as an EFL online learning media, Six students' stated that it made the students feeling happy

CONCLUSION

The teacher has implemented Whatsapp voice chat as media in EFL online learning In three sessions. Every sessions are divided into

three stages such as pre-activity, whilst activity, and post activity. In pre-activity stage, the teacher reinforced the materials in the end of the classroom and the teacher asked the students to standby in Whatsapp group at night. In whilst activity stage, the teacher explained the instructions, slide of PPT, and the example of sentences. The teacher gave the example how to pronounce those sentences using Whatsapp voice chat. Then, the students also record their voice and answer the question that had been provided by the teacher. In this stage also explained the deadline of submission. Lastly, in post activity stage, the teacher gave the student appreciation and evaluation on students' performance so that the students know their strengthen and weakness from the teacher. In conclusion, the EFL online learning using WVC media well implemented, but there is some of students inconsistently following each session.

From eight students' responses, six students also stated that online learning using Voice chat media can help increase their confidence to speaking English. In addition, the students feel happy with the online learning activity.

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